

science and policy
for a healthy future

HORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

WP14 - WP13 Interaction: Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies

Bisphenol A as a case-study

Deliverable Report

AD14.3

WP14 - Biomarkers of Effect

Deadline: November 2018

Upload by Coordinator: 04 April 2019

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marika Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	19/03/2019
Grant Signatory	Argelia Castaño	ISCIII	20/12/2018

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Robert Barouki	INSERM	19/03/2019
Work Package Leader	Nicolás Olea	UGR	20/12/2018
Task leader	Nicolás Olea	UGR	20/12/2018

Responsible author	Vicente Mustieles, Andrea Rodríguez, Mariana F. Fernández, Nicolás Olea	E-mail	vmustieles@ugr.es , andrear@ugr.es , marieta@ugr.es , nolea@ugr.es
Short name of institution	UGR		
Co-authors	Ludek Blaha, Arthur David, Shereen Cynthia, Stephan Couderq, Jean-Baptiste Fini, Tina Kold Jensen, Robert Barouki; Greet Schoeters; Baken Kirsten		

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea N.	Page: 2

Table of contents

Table of contents	2
Authors and acknowledgements.....	3
1 Abstract.....	4
2 Background.....	5
3 Objective	9
4 Selection of effect biomarkers for aligned studies	10
5 Bisphenol A as a case study.....	11
6 Limitations regarding exposure characterisation in HBM4EU aligned studies.....	19
7 Additional technical questions to answer	20
8 Conclusions	21
9 Future Steps	22
10 References.....	23

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 3

Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

Andrea Rodríguez (UGR)

Mariana F. Fernández (UGR)

Nicolás Olea (UGR)

Contributors

Ludek Blaha (MU)

Arthur David (INSERM)

Shereen Cynthia (INSERM)

Stephan Couderq (CNRS)

Jean-Baptiste Fini (CNRS)

Tina Kold Jensen (SDU)

Greet Schoeters (VITO)

Baken Kirsten (VITO)

Robert Barouki (INSERM)

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea N.	Page: 4

1 Abstract

Background: The ultimate objective of the Biomonitoring research is to link biomarkers of exposure to biomarkers of effect and susceptibility to understand the public-health implications of exposure to environmental chemicals.

Objective: The main objective of this additional deliverable was to develop a general strategy for the selection of candidate effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies based on the work conducted inside WP14 and WP13. To provide a practical example, a case study was developed for the bisphenol family of chemical compounds.

Methods: Effect biomarkers used in human epidemiological studies were obtained from the literature searches conducted within WP14 (D14.1, D14.2 and D14.3). Several expert teams with members from both WP14 and WP13 partners were defined during the first Granada Workshop (AD14.2) to join and summarise the experimental and epidemiological data available on effect biomarkers for each family included in the first round of prioritised substances. Knowledge on AOPs and experimental information was gathered inside WP13.

Results: A strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers for their potential implementation in HBM4EU aligned studies has been presented and exemplified in three case studies in relation to the bisphenols family of compounds. The technical and scientific limitations have also been discussed.

Conclusions: This strategy provides the best way to propose and implement effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies, following structured hypotheses on causal relations between exposure and health outcomes strongly substantiated by the available experimental knowledge.

Future Steps: Taking this deliverable as a starting point, all partners from WP14 and WP13 have the compromise to provide a justified selection of the best effect biomarkers for HBM4EU aligned studies, taking into account: i) the specific chemical family; ii) the adverse outcomes of highest concern; iii) pathways supported by an AOP or relevant experimental data; and iv) the critical period of development of interest (children, adolescents or adults).

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 6

Cohort Age	Health Endpoint	Children (6-11 y)	Adolescents (12-19 y)	Adults (20-40 y)
Chemicals	Neurodevelopment	<i>Not measured in children</i>	Neurodevelopment Test: WISC-IV (6-16y) Neurodevelopment Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF), GDNF or Sp4	<i>Not measured in adults</i>
	Reproductive		Reproductive Hormones: LH, FSH, E2, TT, SHBG	
	Endocrine		Thyroid Hormones: TSH, T3, T4	
	Metabolic-Obesity		Glucose metabolism FBG, Fasting insulin levels; HbA1c, HOMA-IR Serum Lipids: LDL, HDL, TC, TG Liver Enzymes: Alanine transaminase (ALT), Aspartate transaminase (AST), Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT), Serum bilirubin. Adipokines: Adiponectin, leptin Others: BMI z-scores; Body fat; Blood pressure. Gene expression of nuclear receptors in blood (monocytes or lymphocytes or whole blood): PPAR α , γ , δ , Genes of cholesterol metabolism: NR1H2 (LXRB), NR1H3 (LXRA), NCEH1, ABCG1 and NPC1 Serum IgE, Absolute eosinophil counts (AEC), eosinophilic cationic	

Effect biomarkers need to be supported by experimental information and available AOPs

The comprehensive literature searches on effect biomarkers conducted by WP14 and summarised in D14.2 showed that some effect biomarkers are specific of particular clinical diseases or physiopathological processes, but in general, effect biomarkers are not specific to particular chemical exposure (D14.2, page 11). Therefore, the selection of effect biomarkers for chemical groups should preferably begin with the identification of the most concerning adverse effects of a given chemical family, primarily based on experimental, but also epidemiological data. Once these adverse outcomes are identified, the experimental information can be organised following the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework (or previously developed AOPs), to identify possible intermediate markers in the causal biological pathway between a particular chemical exposure and a particular adverse outcome. While some of the markers identified using the experimental data coincide with available human effect biomarkers that could be employed in HBM studies, other markers could lead to the development of novel effect biomarkers.

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework

An Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) is “a conceptual framework that portrays existing knowledge concerning the linkage between a direct molecular initiating event and an adverse outcome, at a level of biological organisation relevant to risk assessment” (Ankley et al., 2010). A better understanding of how effect biomarkers are supported by AOPs, could help to use the information gathered to support risk-assessment.

Building an AOP: The main structure of an adverse outcome pathway is the following:

- Molecular initiating event (MIE) – A specialised type of Key Event (KE) that represents the initial point of chemical interaction, on the molecular level, within an organism, that results in a perturbation that starts the AOP.
- Adverse Outcome (AO) – A specialised type of KE that is generally accepted as being of

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 7

regulatory significance on the basis of correspondence to an established protection goal or equivalence to an apical endpoint in an accepted regulatory guideline toxicity test.

Figure 1: AOP main structure, from the molecular initiating event (MIE), through different key events (KEs), to one or more adverse outcomes of regulatory significance.

AOPs can be summarised in the following five points:

1. **AOPs are not specific**, AOPs do not try to describe what a single chemical does, but try to describe what and how any chemical is able to perturb from the MIE, with sufficient potency and duration to produce a biological reason of failure. Thus, the description of AOP does not require chemical-specific information, just to apply those motifs in a predictive context, which requires understanding chemical-specific properties (e.g., potency, ADME) that dictate the magnitude and duration of perturbation at the MIE.
2. **AOPs are modular**: Between two Key events we found which it is called 'Key Events Relationships (KERs)'. KERs consist in a change from one KE to another in which an alteration in the first will determine the next key event in a positive direction or in a negative direction.
3. **AOPs are a pragmatic functional unit of development and evaluation**.
4. For most real-world applications, AOP networks are the functional unit of prediction. By building modular AOPs, it is possible to gradually describe the complexity of potential interactions while meeting systems biology, enhancing the prediction of its possible behavior.

Figure 2: AOP network taken from Dan Villeneuve (EPA) presentation, showed during Mirjam Luijten's training session in the Granada Workshop (AD14.2).

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 8

5. AOPs are living documents: AOPs are a way of organising existing knowledge. As new experiments and data are available, the weight of evidence supporting (or rejecting) KEs relationships will grow and new AOPs and new branches in AOP networks will be discovered. Thus, we are in front of an evolving concept that will grow up with time and research.

WP14-WP13 Interaction

During the first Granada Workshop in 2018 (AD14.2), a better interaction between Work Packages 14 and 13 was planned. The aim was to organise working teams with partners from both WP13 and WP14 focused on each of the chemical families of the first round of prioritised substances, in order to better select human effect biomarkers (identified and summarised by WP14 in D14.3 for the first set of prioritised substances), based on the experimental knowledge summarised by WP13 partners.

Although there are clear differences between animal experimental settings and epidemiological studies, human effect biomarkers (EBM) can represent different stages in many AOPs, and an increasing number of AOPs are including human data. As graphically shown below, EBM could represent early or late key events in a given AOP, which constitutes the basis of the WP14-WP13 interaction:

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 9

3 Objective

The main objective of the current additional deliverable AD14.3 was to present the general strategy for the selection of candidate effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies based on the work conducted inside WP14 and WP13. To provide a practical example, a case study was developed for the bisphenol family of chemical compounds.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 10

4 Selection of effect biomarkers for aligned studies

To develop a timely selection of human effect biomarkers (WP14) taking into account the experimental knowledge developed within WP13 partners, the following steps are proposed:

1. Selection of a chemical family.
2. Identification of the adverse effects or health endpoints of highest concern for the specific chemical family under study based on available animal studies, previous scientific committees and previous expertise of the participants (WP13). Preferentially, no more than 2 or 3 health endpoints should be selected.
3. Consulting the WP14 inventory of human effect biomarkers (D14.3) and list those relevant effect biomarkers according to the selected adverse effects/health endpoints and window of development (children, adolescents or adults).
4. Interaction between WP13 and WP14 partners, to search for available AOPs in the AOP wiki, or previously published AOPs in the literature related to the adverse effects of highest importance identified. If no previous AOP is available, an AOP-like pathway can be constructed with available information. The suitability of using effect biomarkers from the WP14 inventory (D14.3) to represent possible events in AOPs will be discussed by these WP13-WP14 interactions and a justified proposal will be made.
5. At this point, the selection of effect biomarkers has been decided purely based on scientific criteria. In the following and last step, all the WPs involved (WP14, WP13, WP8 and WP11) should finally discuss technical aspects, together with resources issues, that is, try to answer the following questions: i) Can the biomarker be assessed in the available samples from the aligned studies (i.e. urine, blood, serum?); ii) Which team(s) could measure it and with which resources and with which method?; iii) Is there any further limitation that prevents the implementation of a given effect biomarker?

Strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers for HBM4EU aligned studies

Figure 3: Strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers for HBM4EU aligned studies

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 11

5 Bisphenol A as a case study

1. Selection of a chemical family.

The previous general strategy will be exemplified for the bisphenols family of environmental chemicals, with bisphenol A (BPA) being its main representative substance.

2. Identification of the adverse effects or health endpoints of highest concern for bisphenols based on available animal studies, previous scientific committees and previous expertise of the participants (WP13). Preferentially, no more than 2 or 3 health endpoints should be selected.

Biomarkers sufficiently supported by experimental/AOP data were prioritised based on D13.4

Example

For bisphenols, based on previous scientific consensus, expert panels and scientific reviews of the literature, we decided to focus on

- i) reproductive health (Peretz et al., 2014; vom Saal et al., 2007a);
- ii) Metabolic health and obesity (Hwang et al., 2018; Wassenaar et al., 2017); and
- iii) neurodevelopment and neurological effects (Chapin et al., 2008; Mustieles et al., 2015).

The European Food Safety Authority has conducted several risk assessments, the latest one in 2015, in which the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) was lowered from 50 µg/kg bw/day to 4 µg/kg bw/day based on additional information and uncertainties (EFSA 2015a). The adverse outcomes prioritised in additional deliverable 14.3 are in line with many aspects discussed by this EFSA report (EFSA 2015a), but not limited to it. Bench-mark dose chose by EFSA mainly based on a study assessing high BPA doses in relation to reduced kidney weight (EFSA, 2015b). Although this approach is coherent with traditional toxicological assessments, many authors do not agree with this approach since adverse effects at high BPA doses cannot always predict the safety of low doses (Hill et al., 2018), which is supported by experimental results from the recent CLARITY-BPA consortium (Vandenberg et al., 2019). Indeed, at epidemiological and HBM level, low-dose effects of BPA exposure in the kidney are not one of the main human health concerns compared to neurobehavioral, reproductive and metabolic endpoints. Moreover, an increasing number of epidemiologic studies have reported associations between BPA exposure at levels well below the

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 13

4. Interaction between WP13 and WP14 partners, to search for available AOPs in the AOP wiki, or previously published AOPs in the literature related to the adverse effects of highest importance identified. If any previous AOP is available, an AOP-like should be conducted with available information. The suitability of using effect biomarkers from the WP14 inventory (D14.3) to represent possible AOPs will be discussed by these WP13-WP14 and a justified proposal will be made.

Based on all the selected information, the following human effect biomarkers were found to be sufficiently supported by existing AOPs and/or animal studies, and thus of interest for the HBM4EU aligned studies.

A) Bisphenol A and female reproductive health

BPA has been classified as a reproductive toxicant, with a special emphasis on ovarian toxicity (Peretz et al., 2014). Thus, there is increasing concern about the ability of BPA to alter women fertility at different levels (Ziv-Gal and Flaws, 2016), exerting epigenetic effects in the germline and embryos (Santangeli et al., 2017), as well as increasing the risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes such as low birth weight and preterm births (Mustieles et al., 2018; Smarr et al., 2015).

A previously published AOP regarding BPA and alterations in the oestrous cycle was found in the literature (Viguié et al., 2018). In this work, the authors stated:

“Proper cyclicity is essential to reach successful optimal fertility. In rats and mice, BPA exposure is repeatedly and reliably reported to show an adverse effect on the oestrous cycle after exposures at different life stages. In humans, a possible association between modifications of menstrual cycle characteristics (e.g. length of the cycle, duration of menstrual bleeding) and sub-fecundity or spontaneous abortion has been observed. Alterations of ovarian cyclicity can therefore be definitely considered as an adverse health outcome” (Viguié et al., 2018).

After conducting an extensive analysis and integration of previous *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, the authors summarised their proposed AOP between BPA exposure and oestrous cycle alterations in the following figure:

20

C. Viguié et al. / Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology 475 (2018) 10–28

Fig. 4. Sequential cascade from the endocrine effect of BPA to its adverse effects.

A clearly demonstrated target of BPA is aromatase, in the preovulatory follicle. The BPA-induced reduction in the expression of this steroidogenic enzyme induces a reduction in the synthesis of estrogens. Thus, the preovulatory rise of estrogens is attenuated. Consequently, the estrogen-induced gonadotrophins ovulatory surge, is delayed or suppressed, and this induces disturbances in the cycle. Furthermore, BPA may act on the hypothalamo-hypophysis activity.

The authors highlighted the ability of BPA to inhibit the steroid enzyme aromatase in the preovulatory follicle which would cause a reduction in the synthesis of oestrogens, resulting in an attenuated pre-ovulatory rise of oestrogens. Consequently, the oestrogen-induced gonadotropins ovulatory surge could be delayed or suppressed, inducing subsequent disturbances in the cycle.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 14

Moreover, BPA can also act at a central level interfering with the correct functioning of the hypothalamus-pituitary axis, representing a converging effect at both local and central levels, increasing the chances of imbalances in the oestrous cycle (Viguié et al., 2018).

Based on the inventory of human effect biomarkers (D14.3), the following biomarkers could match events in this specific AOP in women:

Chemical compound	MIE/Early KE	KE	AO
Bisphenol A	Gene expression of estrogenic nuclear receptors in blood	LH, FSH, Estradiol, Testosterone, SHBG Kisspeptin?	Altered ovarian cyclicity leading to impaired fertility

Justification: Although to our best knowledge the expression of aromatase in preovulatory follicles cannot be directly assessed in epidemiological studies, the expression of estrogenic nuclear receptors in blood cell populations could provide information about a possible downstream effect of what is happening inside the ovary, providing some mechanistic information. Therefore, **gene expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors** in blood could be representative of an early key event that, although not necessarily a MIE itself, could be related to it. Importantly, urinary BPA concentrations have been previously associated with the *in vivo* gene expression of estrogenic nuclear receptors in male adults (Melzer et al., 2011). Additionally, alterations of steroid hormone levels were identified as key events in the AOP by Viguié et al. (2018). Thus, the measurement of serum luteinizing hormone (**LH**), follicle-stimulating hormone (**FSH**), **estradiol**, **testosterone** and sex hormone-binding globulin (**SHBG**) levels provide a broad picture in order to disentangle possible actions of BPA at both local and systemic levels. Moreover, **kisspeptin** has recently emerged as a key regulator of the mammalian reproductive axis, acting centrally via the kisspeptin receptor, and stimulating the secretion of gonadotrophin releasing hormone (GnRH). When administered to humans in different isoforms, routes and doses, kisspeptin robustly stimulates LH secretion and LH pulse frequency (Clarke et al., 2015; Kurian et al., 2015). Therefore, assessment of serum kisspeptin levels could also provide novel mechanistic information.

Limitations:

1. Although studying the expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors can increase the biological plausibility of epidemiological associations, there are inherent limitations. The predictive potential of assessing expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors in blood cell populations is unclear in relation to female reproductive health among other health effects. In addition, changes in receptor gene expression could be a downstream effect of changes or effects in steroid enzymes and/or hormones, so it cannot be claimed to represent a MIE for sure. However, the information provided by these markers could importantly improve the interpretation of associations with other complementary effect biomarkers, as proposed.
2. Hormones and gonadotrophins are subjected to diurnal and menstrual cycle variations in women, so careful consideration must be given to the timing of blood collection and the day of the oestrous cycle, in order to reduce variability as much as possible
3. The proposed effect biomarkers need to be assessed in blood/serum collected and stored under specific conditions.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 15

B) Bisphenol A and male glucose homeostasis

BPA is a suspected obesogen and metabolic disruptor able to increase adiposity and alter metabolism as shown in experimental models (Heindel et al., 2015; Valentino et al., 2016).

A recent systematic review of experimental studies in rodents has concluded that early-life exposure to BPA may increase adiposity and circulating lipid levels at low doses, and effects tended to be stronger in males (Wassenaar et al., 2017). Moreover, a systematic review and meta-analysis of the epidemiological literature found a significant pooled positive association between urinary BPA concentrations and the risk of type 2 diabetes, as well as positive associations with indicators of impaired fasting glucose and insulin resistance (Song et al., 2016).

Among metabolic outcomes, BPA can target the pancreas at very low doses being able to interfere with insulin function (Alonso-Magdalena et al., 2012; Ropero et al., 2006). Although BPA exposure during pregnancy is generally considered the most sensitive window for disruption of metabolic traits (Alonso-Magdalena et al., 2015), short-term exposure to environmentally relevant levels of BPA can also interfere with glucose homeostasis in adult rats, especially among males (Batista et al., 2012). A human experimental study has also investigated whether BPA alters insulin/C-peptide secretion, suggesting that BPA exposure to a dose considered safe by US regulators may alter glucose-stimulated insulin response in humans (Stahlhut et al., 2018).

Among the mechanisms of action proposed for short-term and rapid actions of BPA in the pancreas are: signaling through estrogen receptor β (Soriano et al., 2012), signaling through non-classical estrogen membrane receptors involving a G-protein-coupled receptor (Alonso-Magdalena et al., 2005) or interacting with different ion channels (Ahn et al., 2018; Soriano et al., 2016).

Based on the previous experimental evidence, and the inventory of human effect biomarkers (D14.3), the following biomarkers could represent a possible causal pathway between BPA exposure and altered insulin and glucose homeostasis in adults, especially in men:

Chemical compound	MIE	KE	AO
Bisphenol A	Gene expression of estrogenic nuclear receptors alpha and beta in blood	Fasting serum glucose, insulin and C-peptide (HOMA-IR, IS and %B). Leptin/adiponectin?	Altered glucose homeostasis leading to type 2 diabetes

Justification: The expression of estrogenic nuclear receptors in blood cell populations could provide information about a possible estrogenic effect of BPA in the pancreas. Therefore, **gene expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors** in blood could be representative of an early key event that, although not necessarily a MIE itself, could be related to it since a rapid effect of BPA in the pancreas of adult male rats through the ER β has been proposed (Soriano et al., 2012).

Fasting serum glucose, insulin and C-peptide can be used to calculate the Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (**HOMA-IR**), but also to calculate the degree of Insulin Sensitivity (**IS**) and the percentage of pancreatic beta-cell function (**%B**), which can be proposed as key events. Adipokines such as leptin and adiponectin could provide additional information.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 16

The demonstration of rapid and short-term effects of BPA in the pancreas in adult experimental animals, supports the implementation of these effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies under a cross-sectional design.

Limitations:

1. Although studying the expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors can increase the biological plausibility of epidemiological associations, there are inherent limitations. Thus, the predictive potential of assessing expression of nuclear estrogenic receptors in blood cell populations is unclear. On the other hand, the abovementioned gene expression could be a downstream effect of changes or effects in steroid enzymes and/or hormones, so it cannot be claimed to represent a MIE for sure. However, the information provided by these markers could importantly improve the interpretation of associations with other complementary effect biomarkers, as proposed.
2. Glucose, insulin and C-peptide levels are subjected to variations depending on the fasting state. Therefore, careful consideration must be given to the timing of blood collection which should be in the early morning and under fasting conditions.
3. Timing of sampling in relation to the time of exposure. Gene expression changes shortly after exposure, while changes in hormone levels may appear later.
4. The proposed effect biomarkers need to be assessed in blood/serum collected and stored under specific conditions.

C) Bisphenol A and neurological effects

One of the greatest concerns about human exposure to low doses of BPA is neurodevelopmental toxicity (Chapin et al., 2008; vom Saal et al., 2007b). There is special concern about the potential effect on the fetus and neonate brain, given their particular vulnerability to neurotoxicants and generally higher exposure to BPA in comparison to adults (Calafat et al., 2008). Although the role of non-persistent chemicals such as BPA on the risk of neurodegenerative diseases has been less explored, studies conducted in adult animals also suggest potential effects (Fang et al., 2016; Masuo and Ishido, 2011).

After performing the literature searches for effect biomarkers (D14.2), although several cognitive and behavioral tests were identified, a big gap in knowledge was observed regarding biochemical or molecular effect biomarkers for BPA effects on the brain. A proposed candidate reported to be affected in experimental studies (Imamura et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2016) and previously implemented in one epidemiological study was Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor (BDNF) (Kundakovic et al., 2015).

BDNF belongs to the neurotrophins family, and regulates neural circuit structure and synaptic plasticity in both the children and the adult brain. BDNF expression and DNA methylation are altered in several psychiatric disorders that are associated with early-life adversity, including depression, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and autism (Cattaneo et al., 2016). Interestingly, several studies have shown that TH can regulate BDNF expression in the brain (Koibuchi et al., 1999; Koibuchi & Chin, 2000; Sui & Li, 2010), with the consequent neurodevelopmental consequences. Additionally, it has also been suggested that BDNF is associated with attention, behavior and cognitive skills in children (Yeom et al., 2016). In vivo, BPA has been associated with inhibition of BDNF in the brain (Wang et al., 2016; Patisaul et al., 2012; Castro et al., 2015). In mice, BDNF DNA methylation in the blood may be used as a predictor of BDNF DNA methylation and gene expression in the hippocampus and of behavioral deficits (Kundakovic et al., 2015).

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 17

Importantly, in human cord blood, prenatal exposure to high BPA levels was associated with methylation of the CpG1B site of the promoter region IV and may represent a biomarker in humans that predicts BDNF gene expression in the brain and consequent alterations in brain function and behavior (Kundakovic et al., 2015). Therefore, it seems there is sufficient experimental support, and suggestive preliminary epidemiological data to propose further research and implementation of BDNF measurements in serum and/or urine (Koven and Collins, 2014), as well as BDNF related epigenetics as novel biomarkers for neurodevelopment.

Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2015 Jun 2;112(22):6807-13. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1408355111. Epub 2014 Nov 10.

DNA methylation of BDNF as a biomarker of early-life adversity.

Kundakovic M¹, Gudsnuik K¹, Herbstman JB², Tang D², Perera FP², Champagne FA³.

Author information

Abstract

Early-life adversity increases the risk for psychopathology in later life. The underlying mechanism(s) is unknown, but epigenetic variation represents a plausible candidate. Early-life exposures can disrupt epigenetic programming in the brain, with lasting consequences for gene expression and behavior. This evidence is primarily derived from animal studies, with limited study in humans due to inaccessibility of the target brain tissue. In humans, although there is evidence for DNA methylation changes in the peripheral blood of psychiatric patients, a fundamental question remains as to whether epigenetic markers in the blood can predict epigenetic changes occurring in the brain. We used in utero bisphenol A (BPA) exposure as a model environmental exposure shown to disrupt neurodevelopment and exert long-term effects on behavior in animals and humans. We show that prenatal BPA induces lasting DNA methylation changes in the transcriptionally relevant region of the *Bdnf* gene in the hippocampus and blood of BALB/c mice and that these changes are consistent with BDNF changes in the cord blood of humans exposed to high maternal BPA levels in utero. Our data suggest that BDNF DNA methylation in the blood may be used as a predictor of brain BDNF DNA methylation and gene expression as well as behavioral vulnerability induced by early-life environmental exposure. Because BDNF expression and DNA methylation are altered in several psychiatric disorders that are associated with early-life adversity, including depression, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and autism, BDNF DNA methylation in the blood may represent a novel biomarker for the early detection of psychopathology.

BPA effects on the brain seem to be more complex compared with other endpoints given the enormous complexity of the central nervous system, and thus existing AOPs and KERs are still lacking (Nesan et al., 2018). BPA acts on hormone receptors and their downstream signaling pathways, and can interfere with hormone synthesis, metabolism, and actions (Gore et al., 2018). Thus, BPA could affect the expression of BDNF through the modulation of calcium ion channels (Imamura et al., 2005).

Based on the previous experimental evidence, and the inventory of human effect biomarkers (D14.3), the following biomarker could mimick a potential key event between BPA exposure and neurological effects:

Chemical compound	MIE	KE	AO
Bisphenol A	Unclear Calcium ion channels? Thyroid signaling? Estrogen signaling?	BDNF methylation in blood	Neurological disease

Justification: There is a big gap in knowledge for molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers for neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative health endpoints. Although the exact mechanisms of action have not been totally elucidated, BDNF and other neurotrophins seem to be affected after BPA exposure in animal studies. Therefore, DNA methylation of serum BDNF can represent a key event for BPA effects on the brain regarding both neurodevelopment and neurodegeneration, given the implication of BDNF in neural plasticity and its relevance for diverse neuropsychiatric disorders.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 18

One of the strengths of assessing DNA methylation of BDNF is that DNA methylation is relatively stable over time, being able to capture more information.

Limitations:

1. The proposed effect biomarker needs to be assessed in blood/serum collected and stored under specific conditions.
2. Need for a specific lab with expertise in epigenetic measurements.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 19

6 Limitations regarding exposure characterisation in HBM4EU aligned studies

In addition to important limitations already acknowledged, it is necessary to add two more considerations regarding exposure characterisation of non-persistent compounds in HBM4EU aligned studies.

A single urine sample to characterise BPA exposure constitutes a limitation that leads to exposure misclassification. However, this would likely result in an underestimation rather than an overestimation of possible BPA effects due to the non-persistent nature and short-term viability of this compound (Perrier et al., 2016). Additionally, although total BPA is assessed in urine, it can account for all routes and exposure sources, and it is regarded as the optimal matrix recommended (Calafat et al., 2015).

Another limitation is that, while urinary BPA concentrations probably reflect short or mid-term exposure, many of the BPA-related adverse effects do not occur immediately (i.e., obesity or type 2 diabetes). However, preclinical alterations may be detected before the onset of an overt disease state, one of the great advantages of using effect biomarkers (DeCaprio, 1997). Moreover, some “immediate” or short-term effects have been reported for BPA in relation to metabolic effects, such as glucose homeostasis, in both experimental animals at very low-doses (Alonso-Magdalena et al., 2012, 2005; Ropero et al., 2006; Soriano et al., 2016), and in human interventional studies (Hagobian et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2018; Stahlhut et al., 2018). Therefore, the proposed relationships between BPA concentrations and hormonal and metabolic effect biomarkers in HBM aligned studies, although subjected to the limitations of all observational studies, might be plausible.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 20

7 Additional technical questions to answer

Specific questions have been asked to the aligned study partners to know whether they have information related to the final selected effect biomarkers.

1. Is the biomarker already assessed or planned to be assessed in some of the aligned studies?

It could be that some classic effect biomarkers such as steroid and thyroid hormones and metabolic parameters (fasting glucose and insulin) have been previously assessed in some of the cohorts participating in the HBM4EU aligned studies.

2. Are the aligned studies interested in the analysis? Who will measure?

UGR (WP14) is already identifying teams that could implement some of the most specific effect biomarkers. As an example, INSERM has successfully measured BDNF DNA methylation in placental samples from the proof of concept (D14.4 and AD14.4), and they could assess it in blood.

3. In which human matrices?

Many of the effect biomarkers need to be assessed using whole blood and/or serum. The availability of these samples, together with details from their collection, storage and preservation need to be provided before undertaking a final decision.

4. With which resources?

Apart from specific budgets directed to this purpose, those partners who will make an additional effort to assess effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies should be supported with more resources at an internal level within their own WPs.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 21

8 Conclusions

The present additional deliverable, including a case study regarding the Bisphenols family, presents the strategy that will be followed for the selection of human effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies. This strategy provides the best way to propose and implement effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies, following structured hypotheses on causal relations between exposure and health outcomes strongly substantiated by the available experimental knowledge.

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 22

9 Future Steps

Taking this deliverable as a starting point, all partners from WP14 and WP13 have the compromise to provide a justified selection of the best effect biomarkers for HBM4EU aligned studies, taking into account:

1. Chemical family,
2. Adverse outcomes of highest concern,
3. Pathway supported by an AOP or relevant experimental data,
4. Critical period of development (children, adolescents or adults).

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 23

10 References

- Ahn, C., Kang, H.-S., Lee, J.-H., Hong, E.-J., Jung, E.-M., Yoo, Y.-M., Jeung, E.-B., 2018. Bisphenol A and octylphenol exacerbate type 1 diabetes mellitus by disrupting calcium homeostasis in mouse pancreas. *Toxicol. Lett.* 295, 162–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2018.06.1071>
- Alonso-Magdalena, P., García-Arévalo, M., Quesada, I., Nadal, Á., 2015. Bisphenol-A treatment during pregnancy in mice: a new window of susceptibility for the development of diabetes in mothers later in life. *Endocrinology* 156, 1659–70. <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2014-1952>
- Alonso-Magdalena, P., Laribi, O., Ropero, A.B., Fuentes, E., Ripoll, C., Soria, B., Nadal, A., 2005. Low doses of bisphenol A and diethylstilbestrol impair Ca²⁺ signals in pancreatic alpha-cells through a nonclassical membrane estrogen receptor within intact islets of Langerhans. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 113, 969–77. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.8002>
- Alonso-Magdalena, P., Ropero, A.B., Soriano, S., García-Arévalo, M., Ripoll, C., Fuentes, E., Quesada, I., Nadal, Á., 2012. Bisphenol-A acts as a potent estrogen via non-classical estrogen triggered pathways. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 355, 201–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2011.12.012>
- Ankley, G.T., Bennett, R.S., Erickson, R.J., Hoff, D.J., Hornung, M.W., Johnson, R.D., Mount, D.R., Nichols, J.W., Russom, C.L., Schmieder, P.K., Serrano, J.A., Tietge, J.E., Villeneuve, D.L., 2010. Adverse outcome pathways: A conceptual framework to support ecotoxicology research and risk assessment. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 29, 730–741. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.34>
- Batista, T.M., Alonso-Magdalena, P., Vieira, E., Amaral, M.E.C., Cederroth, C.R., Nef, S., Quesada, I., Carneiro, E.M., Nadal, A., 2012. Short-term treatment with bisphenol-A leads to metabolic abnormalities in adult male mice. *PLoS One* 7, e33814. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0033814>
- Calafat, A.M., Longnecker, M.P., Koch, H.M., Swan, S.H., Hauser, R., Goldman, L.R., Lanphear, B.P., Rudel, R.A., Engel, S.M., Teitelbaum, S.L., Whyatt, R.M., Wolff, M.S., 2015. Optimal exposure biomarkers for nonpersistent chemicals in environmental epidemiology. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 123, A166-8. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1510041>
- Calafat, A.M., Ye, X., Wong, L.-Y., Reidy, J.A., Needham, L.L., 2008. Exposure of the U.S. population to bisphenol A and 4-tertiary-octylphenol: 2003-2004. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 116, 39–44. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.10753>
- Chapin, R.E., Adams, J., Boekelheide, K., Gray, L.E., Hayward, S.W., Lees, P.S.J., McIntyre, B.S., Portier, K.M., Schnorr, T.M., Selevan, S.G., Vandenbergh, J.G., Woskie, S.R., 2008. NTP-CERHR expert panel report on the reproductive and developmental toxicity of bisphenol A. *Birth Defects Res. B. Dev. Reprod. Toxicol.* 83, 157–395. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdrb.20147>
- Clarke, H., Dhillon, W.S., Jayasena, C.N., 2015. Comprehensive Review on Kisspeptin and Its Role in Reproductive Disorders. *Endocrinol. Metab. (Seoul, Korea)* 30, 124–41. <https://doi.org/10.3803/EnM.2015.30.2.124>
- Committee on Human Biomonitoring for Environmental Toxicants, 2006. Human Biomonitoring for Environmental Chemicals. <https://doi.org/10.17226/11700>
- DeCaprio, 1997. Biomarkers: Coming of age for environmental health and risk assessment. *Environ Sci Technol.* 31 (7), pp 1837–1848. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/es960920aEFSA> 2015a. Scientific Opinion on the risks to public health related to the presence of bisphenol A (BPA) in foodstuffs. *EFSA J.* 13, 3978. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.3978>
- EFSA 2015b. Summary scientific opinion on bisphenol A. www.efsa.europa.eu
- Fang, F., Gao, Y., Wang, T., Chen, D., Liu, J., Qian, W., Cheng, J., Gao, R., Wang, J., Xiao, H.,

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 24

2016. Insulin signaling disruption in male mice due to perinatal bisphenol A exposure: Role of insulin signaling in the brain. *Toxicol. Lett.* 245, 59–67.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2016.01.007>

Gore, A.C., Krishnan, K., Reilly, M.P., 2018. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals: Effects on neuroendocrine systems and the neurobiology of social behavior. *Horm. Behav.* pii: S0018-506X(18)30357-X. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2018.11.006>.

Hagobian, T.A., Bird, A., Stanelle, S., Williams, D., Schaffner, A., Phelan, S., 2019. Pilot study on the effect of orally administered bisphenol A on glucose and insulin response in nonobese adults. *J. Endocr. Soc.* 3, 643–654. <https://doi.org/10.1210/js.2018-00322>

Heindel, J.J., vom Saal, F.S., Blumberg, B., Bovolín, P., Calamandrei, G., Ceresini, G., Cohn, B.A., Fabbri, E., Gioiosa, L., Kassotis, C., Legler, J., La Merrill, M., Rizzir, L., Machtinger, R., Mantovani, A., Mendez, M.A., Montanini, L., Molteni, L., Nagel, S.C., Parmigiani, S., Panzica, G., Paterlini, S., Pomatto, V., Ruzzin, J., Sartor, G., Schug, T.T., Street, M.E., Suvorov, A., Volpi, R., Zoeller, R.T., Palanza, P., 2015. Parma consensus statement on metabolic disruptors. *Environ. Health* 14, 54. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-015-0042-7>

Hill, C.E., Myers, J.P., Vandenberg, L.N., 2018. Nonmonotonic dose–response curves occur in dose ranges that are relevant to regulatory decision-making. *Dose-Response* 16, 155932581879828. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559325818798282>

Hwang, S., Lim, J., Choi, Y., Jee, S.H., 2018. Bisphenol A exposure and type 2 diabetes mellitus risk: a meta-analysis. *BMC Endocr. Disord.* 18, 81. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12902-018-0310-y>
 Yamamura, L., Kurashina, K., Kawahira, T., Omoteno, M., Tsuda, M., 2005. Additional Repression of Activity-Dependent c-fos and BDNF mRNA Expression by Lipophilic Compounds Accompanying a Decrease in Ca²⁺ Influx Into Neurons. *Neurotoxicology* 26, 17–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2004.07.008>

Kundakovic, M., Gudsruk, K., Herbstman, J.B., Tang, D., Perera, F.P., Champagne, F.A., 2015. DNA methylation of BDNF as a biomarker of early-life adversity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112, 6807–6813. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1408355111>

Kurian, J.R., Keen, K.L., Kenealy, B.P., Garcia, J.P., Hedman, C.J., Terasawa, E., 2015. Acute influences of Bisphenol A exposure on hypothalamic release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone and Kisspeptin in female Rhesus Monkeys. *Endocrinology* 156, 2563-70. <http://doi.org/10.1210/en.2014-1634>.

Lee, I., Kim, S., Kim, K.-T., Kim, S., Park, S., Lee, H., Jeong, Y., Lim, J.-E., Moon, H.-B., Choi, K., 2018. Bisphenol A exposure through receipt handling and its association with insulin resistance among female cashiers. *Environ. Int.* 117, 268–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.05.013>

Masuo, Y., Ishido, M., 2011. Neurotoxicity of Endocrine Disruptors: Possible Involvement in Brain Development and Neurodegeneration. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Heal. Part B* 14, 346–369. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2011.578557>

Melzer, D., Harries, L., Cipelli, R., Henley, W., Money, C., McCormack, P., Young, A., Guralnik, J., Ferrucci, L., Bandinelli, S., Corsi, A.M., Galloway, T., 2011. Bisphenol A Exposure Is Associated with *in Vivo* Estrogenic Gene Expression in Adults. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 119, 1788–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1103809>

Mustieles, V., Pérez-Lobato, R., Olea, N., Fernández, M.F., 2015. Bisphenol A: Human exposure and neurobehavior. *Neurotoxicology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2015.06.002>

Mustieles, V., Williams, P.L., Fernandez, M.F., Mínguez-Alarcón, L., Ford, J.B., Calafat, A.M., Hauser, R., Messerlian, C., Environment and Reproductive Health (EARTH) Study Team, 2018. Maternal and paternal preconception exposure to bisphenols and size at birth. *Hum. Reprod.* 33, 1528–1537. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dey234>

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 25

- Nesan, D., Sewell, L.C., Kurrasch, D.M., 2018. Opening the black box of endocrine disruption of brain development: Lessons from the characterization of Bisphenol A. *Horm. Behav.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yhbeh.2017.12.001>
- Peretz, J., Vrooman, L., Ricke, W.A., Hunt, P.A., Ehrlich, S., Hauser, R., Padmanabhan, V., Taylor, H.S., Swan, S.H., VandeVoort, C.A., Flaws, J.A., 2014. Bisphenol a and reproductive health: update of experimental and human evidence, 2007-2013. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 122, 775–86. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1307728>
- Perrier, F., Giorgis-Allemand, L., Slama, R., Philippat, C., 2016. Within-subject pooling of biological samples to reduce exposure misclassification in biomarker-based studies. *Epidemiology* 27, 378–88. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000000460>
- Ropero, A.B., Alonso-Magdalena, P., Ripoll, C., Fuentes, E., Nadal, A., 2006. Rapid endocrine disruption: environmental estrogen actions triggered outside the nucleus. *J. Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 102, 163–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsbmb.2006.09.019>
- Santangeli, S., Maradonna, F., Olivotto, I., Piccinetti, C.C., Giocchini, G., Carnevali, O., 2017. Effects of BPA on female reproductive function: The involvement of epigenetic mechanism. *Gen. Comp. Endocrinol.* 245, 122–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2016.08.010>
- Smarr, M.M., Grantz, K.L., Sundaram, R., Maisog, J.M., Kannan, K., Louis, G.M.B., 2015. Parental urinary biomarkers of preconception exposure to bisphenol A and phthalates in relation to birth outcomes. *Environ. Heal.* 14, 73. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-015-0060-5>
- Song, Y., Chou, E.L., Baecker, A., You, N.-C.Y., Song, Y., Sun, Q., Liu, S., 2016. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals, risk of type 2 diabetes, and diabetes-related metabolic traits: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Diabetes* 8, 516–32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-0407.12325>
- Soriano, S., Alonso-Magdalena, P., García-Arévalo, M., Novials, A., Muhammed, S.J., Salehi, A., Gustafsson, J.-A., Quesada, I., Nadal, A., 2012. Rapid Insulinotropic Action of Low Doses of Bisphenol-A on Mouse and Human Islets of Langerhans: Role of Estrogen Receptor β . *PLoS One* 7, e31109. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0031109>
- Soriano, S., Ripoll, C., Alonso-Magdalena, P., Fuentes, E., Quesada, I., Nadal, A., Martinez-Pinna, J., 2016. Effects of Bisphenol A on ion channels: Experimental evidence and molecular mechanisms. *Steroids* 111, 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.steroids.2016.02.020>
- Stahlhut, R.W., Myers, J.P., Taylor, J.A., Nadal, A., Dyer, J.A., vom Saal, F.S., 2018. Experimental BPA Exposure and Glucose-Stimulated Insulin Response in Adult Men and Women. *J. Endocr. Soc.* 2, 1173–1187. <https://doi.org/10.1210/js.2018-00151>
- Valentino, R., D’Esposito, V., Ariemma, F., Cimmino, I., Beguinot, F., Formisano, P., 2016. Bisphenol A environmental exposure and the detrimental effects on human metabolic health: is it necessary to revise the risk assessment in vulnerable population? *J. Endocrinol. Invest.* 39, 259–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40618-015-0336-1>
- Vandenberg, L.N., Hunt, P.A., Gore, A.C., 2019. Endocrine disruptors and the future of toxicology testing — lessons from CLARITY–BPA. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-019-0173-y>
- Viguié, C., Mhaouty-Kodja, S., Habert, R., Chevrier, C., Michel, C., Pasquier, E., 2018. Evidence-based adverse outcome pathway approach for the identification of BPA as an endocrine disruptor in relation to its effect on the estrous cycle. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 475, 10–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2018.02.007>
- vom Saal, F.S., Akingbemi, B.T., Belcher, S.M., Birnbaum, L.S., Crain, D.A., Eriksen, M., Farabollini, F., Guillette, L.J., Hauser, R., Heindel, J.J., Ho, S.-M., Hunt, P.A., Iguchi, T., Jobling, S., Kanno, J., Keri, R.A., Knudsen, K.E., Laufer, H., LeBlanc, G.A., Marcus, M., McLachlan, J.A., Myers, J.P., Nadal, A., Newbold, R.R., Olea, N., Prins, G.S., Richter, C.A.,

AD14.3 - Delineation of AOPs for the selection of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies - Bisphenol A as a case-study	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect biomarkers	Version: 2.0
Authors: V. Mustieles, A. Rodríguez-Carrillo, MF Fernández, N. Olea	Page: 26

Rubin, B.S., Sonnenschein, C., Soto, A.M., Talsness, C.E., Vandenberg, J.G., Vandenberg, L.N., Walser-Kuntz, D.R., Watson, C.S., Welshons, W. V, Wetherill, Y., Zoeller, R.T., 2007a. Chapel Hill bisphenol A expert panel consensus statement: integration of mechanisms, effects in animals and potential to impact human health at current levels of exposure. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 24, 131–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2007.07.005>

vom Saal, F.S., Akingbemi, B.T., Belcher, S.M., Birnbaum, L.S., Crain, D.A., Eriksen, M., Farabollini, F., Guillette, L.J., Hauser, R., Heindel, J.J., Ho, S.-M., Hunt, P.A., Iguchi, T., Jobling, S., Kanno, J., Keri, R.A., Knudsen, K.E., Laufer, H., LeBlanc, G.A., Marcus, M., McLachlan, J.A., Myers, J.P., Nadal, A., Newbold, R.R., Olea, N., Prins, G.S., Richter, C.A., Rubin, B.S., Sonnenschein, C., Soto, A.M., Talsness, C.E., Vandenberg, J.G., Vandenberg, L.N., Walser-Kuntz, D.R., Watson, C.S., Welshons, W. V, Wetherill, Y., Zoeller, R.T., 2007b. Chapel Hill bisphenol A expert panel consensus statement: integration of mechanisms, effects in animals and potential to impact human health at current levels of exposure. *Reprod. Toxicol.* 24, 131–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2007.07.005>

Wang, C., Li, Z., Han, H., Luo, G., Zhou, B., Wang, S., Wang, J., 2016. Impairment of object recognition memory by maternal bisphenol A exposure is associated with inhibition of Akt and ERK/CREB/BDNF pathway in the male offspring hippocampus. *Toxicology* 341–343, 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2016.01.010>

Wassenaar, P.N.H., Trasande, L., Legler, J., 2017. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Early-Life Exposure to Bisphenol A and Obesity-Related Outcomes in Rodents. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 125, 106001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP1233>

Ziv-Gal, A., Flaws, J.A., 2016. Evidence for bisphenol A-induced female infertility: a review (2007–2016). *Fertil. Steril.* 106, 827–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2016.06.027>